

1 **Trastuzumab resistance features TAOK2 activation.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We studied whole tumor gene expression in humans with pathologic complete response (pCR) or
7 residual disease (RD) following treatment for HER2+ breast cancer to discover gene expression changes
8 associated with, resulting from or causing resistance to treatment with the HER2-targeted treatment
9 trastuzumab (Herceptin). We identified activation of TAOK2 in humans whose tumors display resistance
10 to treatment with trastuzumab. Studying whole transcription in HER2+ breast cancer cells engineered to
11 develop trastuzumab-resistance *in vitro* validated this phenomena. TAOK2 activation likely supports
12 resistance to trastuzumab in humans with HER2+ breast cancer.
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28